

The bitter taste of vitamins is mediated by human TAS2R activation

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Abstract

Vitamins play an important role in maintaining normal physiologic and metabolic functions. Vitamins are known to generate bitterness, which may contribute to the off-taste of nutritional supplements. This negative sensation may decrease product acceptability and patient compliance. Few studies have examined taste thresholds and sensory sensing mechanisms at the origin of vitamin taste detection. To better understand vitamin bitterness perception, we combined human sensory analysis and taste receptor functional assays. We measured the aqueous taste detection threshold of four B vitamins using sensory difference tests. Challenging the 25 human bitter taste 2 receptors (TAS2Rs), we found that three vitamins stimulated one or more receptors. For each positive molecule-TAS2R combination, we measured the half-maximum effective concentrations (EC₅₀). Thus, we found that the combination of sensory and biological data can provide useful explanations for the bitter detection of vitamins.

Keywords: vitamins, bitter, bitter taste threshold, cellular assay, sensory studies

Introduction

Many bitter molecules present in food have beneficial effects on health, such as polyphenols, amino acids, minerals, and vitamins. Although vitamins supply no energy, they are essential for correct human body function. The current classification system, based on physicochemical, storage and excretion properties, divides the thirteen known vitamins into two groups called water-soluble and fat-soluble vitamins. These nutrients are involved in various physiological and biochemical processes that are essential for the proper functioning of the human body [1]. The human body is able to synthesise two vitamins (phyloquinone and calciferol); the others must be provided by a healthy and varied diet. During certain pathologies and/or difficult access to healthy food, vitamin deficiencies may occur in some people. To prevent these deficiencies, vitamin intake in the form of nutritional supplements or supplemented foods is strongly recommended. When taken in the mouth, vitamins can be perceived with a bitter off-taste, leading to a decrease in product acceptability and patient compliance [2]. Although their use in medicine is common, little is known about the taste threshold and sensory sensing mechanism involved in vitamin bitter taste detection. In humans, bitter taste is detected through the activation of 25 bitter taste receptors (TAS2Rs) belonging to the class A subfamily of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs) [3]. A previous study demonstrated that thiamine hydrochloride (a vitamin B1 analogue) is able to activate two TAS2Rs (TAS2R1 and TAS2R39) [4]. However, no information is available on other vitamins.

To better understand the mechanisms involved in bitterness perception, we combined taste receptor functional assays and human sensory analysis. First, we challenged the 25 human TAS2Rs with eleven vitamins. For each positive molecule-receptor combination, we measured the half-maximum effective concentrations (EC₅₀). We then determined the bitter taste recognition threshold of four native or analogue vitamins in aqueous solution (thiamine hydrochloride, riboflavin phosphate, niacinamide, pyridoxine hydrochloride) that exhibit a strong bitter taste.

Experimental

Chemicals

Thirteen native or analogue vitamins were provided by Bayer SAS (Global Innovation Centre, Gaillard, France): thiamine hydrochloride (B1); riboflavin phosphate (B2), niacinamide (B3), calcium pantothenate (B5), pyridoxine hydrochloride (B6), biotin (B8), folic acid (B9), cobalamin (B12), ascorbic acid (C), retinal (A), calciferol (D), phyloquinone (K), and α -tocopherol acetate (E).

Receptor Functional Assay

HEK293T-Ga16gust44 cells were seeded on poly-D-lysine-coated 96-well black microplates. After overnight growth, the cells were transiently transfected with the 25 TAS2R expression plasmids using Lipofectamine 2000TM (Life Technologies). Twenty hours later, the cells were loaded with Fluo4-AM for 1 hour. The fluorescence signal was recorded at 510 nm after excitation at 488 nm using the fluorescence microplate reader FlexStation 3

(Molecular Devices). Given that some compounds studied could interfere with cellular viability and calcium assays, they were tested on mock-transfected cells. All vitamins were tested except riboflavin phosphate and niacinamide, which possess intrinsic fluorescence, making them incompatible with the assay. Vitamins were prepared in adapted buffer and tested at different concentrations between 1 μ M and 30 mM. The ratio between maximum variations in fluorescence after ligand addition and initial fluorescence before addition ($\Delta F/F$) was calculated for each well to generate a dose-response curve. The dose-response data were fitted, and EC_{50} values were calculated using a four-parameter logistic equation (SigmaPlot, Systat Software, San Jose, CA).

Human Sensory Analysis

To evaluate the bitterness of vitamins that have not been included in the cell-based assay and to compare *in vitro* and *in vivo* results, we conducted human sensory experiments. The bitter taste detection thresholds of four vitamins (thiamine hydrochloride, riboflavin phosphate, niacinamide, and pyridoxine hydrochloride) were determined by 32 panellists using a discriminative sensory test called three-alternative forced choice (3-AFC) [5]. Samples are presented in black glasses and under red light. Evaluation was conducted with a nose clip, and four repetitions were performed per subject for each tested vitamin. The best estimate threshold method was used to calculate the bitter taste detection threshold of each compound [6]. The vitamin concentrations used were determined according to the daily reference intake, quantities present in the nutritional supplements and toxicity thresholds. The compounds were diluted in water (Evian water, France). This sensory experiment was approved by an ethical committee (Personal Protection Committee 2018-A01342-53).

Results and discussion

To identify the bitter taste receptors activated by the tested vitamins, 25 human TAS2Rs were transiently expressed in HEK293T cells stably expressing the chimeric G protein $G\alpha 16gust44$. Calcium imaging experiments showed that two vitamins activated only one TAS2R. Therefore, calciferol (vitamin D) and retinal (vitamin A) activate TAS2R10 and TAS2R38, respectively. We observed that pyridoxine hydrochloride (the vitamin B6 analogue) activates two TAS2RS proteins, namely, TAS2R7 and TAS2R14. We determined dose-response curves by stimulating transfected cells with increasing concentrations of bitter vitamins (Figure 1), yielding EC_{50} values of 250 and 300 μ M for the TAS2R10-calciferol and TAS2R38-retinal pairs, respectively. Concerning pyridoxine hydrochloride, we measured similar EC_{50} values (10.25 and 25.52 mM) for the two activated receptors, TAS2R7 and TAS2R14, respectively. Comparing the EC_{50} values of each vitamin-receptor pair (Figure 1), we observed that the two fat-soluble vitamins activated bitter taste receptors at lower concentrations than water-soluble vitamins.

Figure 1: Dose-response curve and EC_{50} value of cell lines transiently expressed TAS2Rs stimulated by three vitamins: pyridoxine hydrochloride, retinal and calciferol.

Our cellular assay detects the cellular response to bitter compounds using a calcium-sensitive fluorescent dye [4]. Therefore, this method cannot be applied to fluorescent vitamins, such as riboflavin phosphate and niacinamide. To evaluate their potential bitterness, we performed human sensory experiments. In addition, to compare *in vitro* and *in vivo* results, two other vitamins previously identified as bitter were included in the sensory analysis. We measured the bitter taste detection threshold of these four vitamins (Figure 2). With a cut-off value between 1.1 and 5.5 mM, we found that thiamine hydrochloride, niacinamide and pyridoxine hydrochloride had a

lower activation potency than riboflavin phosphate (0.65 mM). These sensory experiments confirmed the bitterness of two other vitamins not tested in the cellular assay, riboflavin phosphate and niacinamide.

Figure 2: Human bitter taste recognition threshold (mol/L) of four water-soluble vitamins: (A) thiamine hydrochloride, (B) riboflavin phosphate, (C) niacinamide, and (D) pyridoxine hydrochloride

As observed in some studies, the data collected relative to the cellular assay are not in perfect agreement with human bitterness perception [7, 8]. Table 1 summarises the bitter taste threshold of some vitamins (from cell-based assay and/or sensory analysis) and their calculated molar concentration in standard nutritional supplements (based on the recommendations of pharmaceutical companies and consumer habits). Comparing the data obtained, we observed that the bitter taste threshold measured using the cellular-based assay was lower than the bitter taste threshold determined by the 32 assessors. For example, the bitter taste threshold for thiamine hydrochloride differs by a factor of ~10 between *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments. The same observation was done for pyridoxine hydrochloride (a factor of ~5). Our data demonstrated a slight difference between human bitter vitamin perception and TAS2R activation in a taste receptor functional assay. This difference can have different origins at both peripheral and central levels.

Table 1: Comparison between human bitter detection threshold, cellular bitter detection threshold and concentration in nutritional supplement studied for six bitter vitamins.

Vitamin	Cellular bitter detection threshold (mM)	Human bitter detection threshold (mM)	* Concentration in nutritional supplement (mM)
Thiamine hydrochloride	0.10	1.10	0.44
Riboflavin phosphate	ND	0.65	0.40
Niacinamide	ND	5.50	4.06
Pyridoxine hydrochloride	1	5.20	0.73
Retinal	0.05	ND	0.03
Calciferol	0.05	ND	0.01x10 ⁻⁰⁵

Cellular taste threshold refers to the minimum concentration of vitamin able to activate TAS2R.

* Calculated concentration for a nutritional supplement (Berocca©, Bayer France) dissolved in 100 mL of water. ND, not determined.

Conclusion

Combining cellular assays and psychometric data, we identified vitamins with bitter taste with different threshold values resulting from *in vivo* and *in vitro* experiments. These differences may be due to absorption by the oral epithelium or/and the interaction of bitter compounds with salivary proteins as previously suggested [7, 8]. However, our study revealed that the vitamin concentrations present in the nutritional supplements cannot contribute to their off-taste or bitter taste (Table 1). This observation could be linked to the presence of other nutrients, such as minerals, which have a strong bitter taste [2], and/or additive effects between bitter compounds [7]. Thus, our data provide information on bitter vitamin concentrations that should not be exceeded to develop a nutritional supplement with better organoleptic qualities and consumer acceptability.

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